

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

AUV observations under the sea ice around grounded icebergs

Deliverable D2.2

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Cover sheet: Photograph of AUV Ran near Bear Ridge in the Amundsen Sea, photo by Anna Wåhlin.

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History of changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	17 October 2024	Submitted version	Anna Wåhlin
Version 2	6 March 2026	Revision in sections: 2.2 and 2.3 with the addition of the datasets and links. Integration of section 3 with a more text on the analysis	Anna Wåhlin

1. Publishable summary

This deliverable comprises a high-resolution bathymetry dataset acquired using an AUV-mounted multibeam in an ice-covered region near Bear Ridge in the Amundsen Sea. In total, we obtained 25 km² of high-resolution bathymetry (1 m grid size). This can be compared to the resolution normally obtained from a ship-borne multibeam, which is 10-20 m. An initial assessment of the traces seen is also provided.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Field work

Fieldwork was conducted aboard the Korean icebreaker RV/IB Araon from 28 December 2023 to 15 February 2024 (Lee et al., 2024). During the expedition, two autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) missions were conducted to survey the bathymetry beneath fast sea ice in the vicinity of Bear Ridge (Fig. 1). The AUV was equipped with sensors that measured in situ water properties and remote-sensing (acoustic) sensors. The acoustic sensors are two Doppler velocity loggers (DVL) operated at 500 kHz frequency, one looking up and one looking down, that are always operating; a downward-looking multibeam of type EM2040 that can operate at 200, 300, or 400 kHz; and a second multibeam of type EM2040C that can be mounted looking upwards. It is standard practice that, before the mission begins, a choice must be made among the multibeam systems to collect data from, as they cannot be operated simultaneously or switched between during the mission. This report outlines the results from missions ANA14B_02 and ANA14B_03, which were conducted at 50-80 m above the seabed with the downward-looking multibeam operational.

Figure 1. Maps of the survey region. (A) Bathymetry from ship multibeam and gravity inversion (pale colours). The colored dots show the turbidity along the AUV mission paths. (B) Overview of the Amundsen Sea with the AUV survey area indicated by the red square.

Fig. 1: Maps of the survey region. (A) Bathymetry from ship multibeam and gravity inversion (pale colours). The coloured dots indicate turbidity along the AUV mission paths. (B) Overview of the Amundsen Sea with the AUV survey area indicated by the red square.

2.1.2 AUV missions near Bear Ridge

Both AUV missions were successful, and all sensors operated without error throughout. Before the first dive, we deployed a cNode near the launch and recovery position (red circle in Fig. 2), ensuring that navigation remained highly accurate throughout the dive. Tables 1 and 2 show the technical summary of the dives.

2.1.3 Deviations from the original plan

The original plan was to deploy the AUV to access Bear Ridge from the west, enabling surveys of the area where B22 was previously grounded. Due to heavy sea-ice cover, we instead accessed the deeper area east of Bear Ridge. Nevertheless, the deliverable has been provided, and the dataset has been retrieved.

Fig. 2: Bathymetry in the surveyed area. A) Overview of the surveyed area with sea ice and ice shelf indicated by shaded regions, pinning point indicated by brown, the bathymetry in the surveyed region shown as a coloured map and tracks, and the zoomed-in areas in (B) - (D) indicated by colored rectangles. The red circle indicates the position of the cNode navigation beacon. For the location of the survey in the Amundsen Sea, see Fig. 1. B) zoomed in area of a deeper portion of the bathymetry, average depth 1400 m. The location of the zoomed area is shown in A by a red rectangle. C) zoomed in area of the foot of one of the steep parts, average depth 1000 m. The location of the zoomed area is shown in A by a blue rectangle. D) zoomed in area of a steep slope, average depth 900 m. Location of the zoomed area is shown in A by a black rectangle.

2.2 References

- Lee, W. S. et al, 2024. Thwaites Glacier Expedition 2023–2024 (ANA14B). Cruise report. KOPRI has made this available on the [SAON database](#).
- Graham, A., Wåhlin, A., Hogan, K., Nitsche, F. Heywood, K., Totten, R. Smith, J., Hillenbrand, C., Simkins, L., Anderson, J., Wellner, J. and R. D. Larter, 2022. Rapid retreat of Thwaites Glacier in the pre-satellite era. *Nature Geoscience*, 15 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-01019-9>

2.3 Open Science

The data obtained from the AUV surveys is published in the open-access data repository, the Swedish National Data Service, with the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5878/ns3m-fs31>. They can be cited as Wåhlin, A., Stedt, F., Wahlgren, S., Yuan, X., Billman, M., & Lee, W. S. (2026). *Raw data from Ran AUV*

missions ANA14B_01, ANA14B_02 and ANA14B_03 performed during the ANA14B RVIB Araon expedition to the Amundsen Sea (Version 1) [Data set]. Göteborgs universitet. <https://doi.org/10.5878/ns3m-fs31>

The following publication was published in January 2026 based on this data set: Hank K., Arthern R.J., Williams C.R., Brisbourne A.M., Smith A.M., Smith J.A., Wåhlin A., Anandkrishnan S., 2026. Inferring the ice sheet sliding law from seismic observations: A Pine Island Glacier case study. Cryosphere, 20 (1), pp. 495 - 510. DOI: [10.5194/tc-20-495-2026](https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-20-495-2026)

Table 1: Technical summary of the first dive, ANA14B_02.

ANA14B_02 GÖTEBORGS UNIVERSITET			
RV Araon 2024 / 12 January 2024			
Mission Objective	Mission Description		Launch notes
Mapping sea ice draft and bathymetry preparing for more dives. Bathymetry is slightly tricky with steep areas.	First dive under thwaites. Cnode deployed.		
Sensor	Configuration	Comment	Troubleshooting
Upward Looking MBES	No		
ADCP Pinnacle	Yes		Stopped logging data mid-mission.
Upward Looking Altimeter	No		
Water sampler	No		
Seabird CTD			Stbd oxygen sensor (3700) did not respond to changes.
DVL			
Other			Rudder comp appeared to be leaking, we removed a suspicious connector.
Buoyancy Description (ref bouyancy log RevD)			
Surface	Depth	Comment	
	27	22	
Hugin OS operator:	Anna		
Deck crew:	Filip, Anders, Maja		
Date	Time (UTC)	Op.	Event

Table 2: Technical summary of the second dive, ANA14B_03.

ANA14B_03 RV Araon 2024 / 15 January 2024				
Mission Objective	Mission Description		Launch notes	Recovery notes
Second dive under Thwaites, objective to survey more of the bathymetry (preparing for a third dive potentially looking at the ice).				Emergency ascent because AUV trainee (Maja) did not properly attach the CO2 bottle, bladder never filled.
Sensor	Configuration	Comment	Troubleshooting	
Upward Looking MBES	No			
ADCP Pinnacle	Yes	Re-formatted the sd-memory card of the Pinnacle and changed batteries.		
Upward Looking Altimeter	No			
Water sampler	No			
Seabird CTD	Oxygen sensors 2637 stbd &	Swapped out the STBD oxygen sensor to s/r	Port sensor shows strange values, we suspect conductivity sensor drift.	
DVL				
Other				
Buoyancy Description (ref buoyancy log RevD)				
Surface	Depth	Comment		
	20	24		
Hugin OS operator:	Anna			
Deck crew:	Filip, Anders, Maja			
Date	Time (UTC)	Op.	Event	

3. Results

The primary deliverable is the bathymetric dataset. Figure 2 shows the area surveyed together with examples of zoomed-in parts of the seabed where traces of moving ice can be seen. The resolution is similar to that obtained in 2019 from the same system (Graham et al., 2022). The average depth at the survey site is 1200 m, and scourge marks at the lower levels are not likely to arise from icebergs. However, marks on the higher hill tops can be made by icebergs.

It was shown by Hank et al. (2026) that slipperiness at the ice-sheet base and how it is parameterised in glaciological projections are key uncertainties for future projections of sea-level rise. By quantifying acoustic propagation through the ice, we could get information about the effective pressure, which is a key control of basal sliding. This identified a link between seismic observations and sliding-law parameters, which can be applied to acoustic impedance in glacial environments underlain by granular material, and supports a Coulomb-type sliding law in rapidly sliding tributaries such as Pine Island Glacier.

The sliding laws examined represent sliding over different subglacial beds, and after analyses the effective pressure was estimated by rearranging the sliding laws. Substituting the estimated effective pressure into separate models and using independent estimates for grain diameter and porosity from sediment cores provides an estimate of acoustic impedance for each sliding law, which was then compared to acoustic data collected at five sites (Fig. 3). Data points are treated as independent: a sub-sampled data set (every 10th data point) generally yields the same conclusions (Hank et al, 2026).

Fig.3 (from Hank et al, 2026): Acoustic impedance observations (Brisbourne et al., 2017) compared with model predictions based on different sliding laws according to legend. (a) - (e) The observational uncertainties are shown as error bars. (f) Basal sliding speed in the Amundsen Sea Embayment from inversion. The arrows mark the location of the data sites. Except for site iSTARit, all data were collected on fast-flowing tributaries of PIG (Brisbourne et al., 2017).

References:

Brisbourne, A. M., Smith, A. M., Vaughan, D. G., King, E. C., Davies, D., Bingham, R. G., Smith, E. C., Nias, I. J., and Rosier, S. H.: Bed conditions of Pine Island Glacier, West Antarctica, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 122, 419–433, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JF004033>, 2017.

Graham, A., Wåhlin, A., Hogan, K., Nitsche, F. Heywood, K., Totten, R. Smith, J., Hillenbrand, C., Simkins, L., Anderson, J., Wellner, J. and R. D. Larter, 2022. Rapid retreat of Thwaites Glacier in the pre-satellite era. *Nature Geoscience*, 15 (9).

Hank K., Arthern R.J., Williams C.R., Brisbourne A.M., Smith A.M., Smith J.A., Wåhlin A., Anandakrishnan S., 2026. Inferring the ice sheet sliding law from seismic observations: A Pine Island Glacier case study. *Cryosphere*, 20 (1), pp. 495 - 510. DOI: 10.5194/tc-20-495-2026

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives, as described in the action description.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

The deliverable provides three high-resolution bathymetric datasets that reveal historical traces of ice-sheet-ocean processes. The data sets pertain to warm ice shelves influenced by grounded icebergs. It also provides clues about vertical/horizontal mixing, ocean heat delivery, iceberg interactions with sea ice, bathymetry, and basal melt.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-climate models.

This deliverable contributes by using new and existing datasets to improve ice sheet model initialisation and to quantify the uncertainty in present-day freshwater fluxes from Antarctica due to climate variability, dynamical processes (calving, ice flow), and surface/basal mass balance (surface runoff, basal melt).

O6: Assess the ocean impact on, and feedbacks between, key global climate metrics (e.g. SLR, global mean surface temperature) and polar ice sheet melt to 2300 and beyond.

This deliverable provides new datasets of iceberg traces, which can be used to reconstruct past iceberg drift tracks as well as the behaviour of other parts of the moving ice sheet. This will improve the representation of icebergs and ice-shelf processes in models, including coupled ice-sheet-climate models. It will improve predictions of the impact and likelihood of ice-sheet melt scenarios, including crossing tipping points, as well as of global consequences, such as changes in SRL and AMOC states.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

This deliverable contributes three new high-resolution bathymetric datasets to open data repositories, findable and integrating with, among others, SOOS, EMODnet and Copernicus. Data consolidation and delivery will be achieved through close integration with SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus data delivery services, and will follow FAIR principles and be INSPIRE-compliant. Direct partnership with SOOS, SAMOC, EPB, EU Polar Cluster, EU-PolarNet 2, and other European and international programmes, as well as the high-level involvement of investigators in international science coordination, climate assessment and policy bodies, will maximise the reach and impact of OCEAN ICE.